

Effect of Financial Performance on Corporate Social Responsibility of Listed Non-Financial Firms in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines financial performance and Corporate Social Responsibility of listed Non-financial firms in Nigeria for a period of ten years from January 2009 to December 2018. It has been argued that firms with better performance are expected to engage more in Corporate Social Responsibility and consider public interest in corporate decision making. The population of this study covers all the seventy five (75) listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. Out of the 75 listed non financial firms in Nigeria, fifty six (56) firms were selected as sample. Thus, filtering out 18 firms that were listed before January 2009. Specifically, the impact of return on assets, return on equity, return on investment, and net profit margin on Corporate Social Responsibility of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria is investigated using firm size and firm growth as control variables. The study employs correlational and expo-facto research designs using panel multiple regression as techniques of data analysis. Quantitative approach was adopted in the study and the study aligns to positivist paradigm. The study reveals that return on assets, return on investment and net profit margin are positively, strongly, and statistically significant in determining the Corporate Social Responsibility at 1% level of significance respectively. While, return on equity also positively influences the Corporate Social Responsibility of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria at 5% level of significance. The result implies that financial performance influences non-financial firms in Nigeria. The study concludes that non-financial firms with high performance invest more into Corporate Social Services than low performing once. Therefore, the study recommends amongst others that the management of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria should acquire more assets, and issue more shares to prospective investors to improve returns and performance for better corporate social services to their host communities. Again, the management of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria should improve their internal control mechanism for cost reduction and increase of net profit margin. While for return on investment, the management of listed non-financial firms should maintain quality assets that are durable.

Keywords: Financial Performance, Corporate Social Responsibility

1 Introduction

Every business's existence and long-term survival are dependent on the achievement of its goals. Economic and social objectives are the two broad categories of business objectives that business entities are expected to achieve. While economic objectives are the goals that an organization must achieve through its business efforts, social objectives are the goals that an organization must achieve in order to satisfy the interests of its shareholders, employees, and the general public (Krishna & Rao, 2002). The international community's interest in the conflict between oil and gas companies and their host communities prompted the development of CSR in Nigeria in the 1990s (Oguntade & Mafimisebi, 2011). CSR is a fundamental requirement for examining the relationship between business organizations and society. According to Onwuchekwa (2002), in Nigeria, the expectation of social service from oil companies has risen dramatically, particularly in oil-producing areas, and the failure of those companies to meet those expectations has resulted in a very turbulent environment for them. Managers who ignore stakeholder claims on their organizations are more likely to lose support from those stakeholders, which could hurt the performance of the affected companies. As a result, it is critical for managers to take stakeholder claims seriously when making CSR-related decisions (Hill & McShane, 2008).

The performance measured by Return on Asset (ROA) is expected to go a long way in explaining and determining the extent of variation in CSR investment by the listed non financial firms in Nigeria. This is further buttressed by Song and Zu (2009) that the better-off a firm is, the more likely its manager is to get involved in CSR activities and also a postulation that when a firm has a high return on assets, it may likely be

encouraged to invest in CSR. The ability of excess funds invested elsewhere to generate revenue that can be used to improve the firm participating in CSR as measured by CSR information is known as return on investment (ROI). Patten and Adams posited that Companies that impact more on the environment are those that disclose more social and environmental information extensively and frequently than others because there is more public pressure on the company (Adams et al., 1998; Patten, 1991). Do the factors that have been previously documented to determine CSR in developed and developing economies apply to Nigerian firms? Hence, this study seeks to contribute to the existing empirical literatures in this area by examining the extent to which ROA and ROE, ROI and NPM impacts on CSR of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

In addition, most of the studies (Abdur-Roufand; Akrouf & Ben-Othman 2013; Ebiringa *et al.* 2013 & Faris *et al.* 2012), conducted in this area made use of ordinary least square multiple regression and Chi-square techniques. These techniques fail in reflecting time variant and character specific issues, conducting fixed and random effects, Hausman specification test and related robustness tests. This study therefore uses a more robust regression technique (GLS multiple regression technique) to address deficiencies in the OLS and Chi-square analysis techniques.

Finally, most of the studies were conducted in advanced economies, only few studies (Li & Zhang, 2010; Reverte, 2009; Wang & Song, 2011) were conducted in developing economies. There is also a gap in terms of people's ethical reasoning and decision, environment, period, methodologies employed and industries used by other studies. Thus, this study fills the gap by assessing the impact of financial performance on CSR of non-financial firms in Nigeria. This study raises and seeks to provide answers to the following questions:

- i. To what extent does ROA affect of return on asset on CSR of non-financial firms listed in Nigeria?
- ii. To what extent does ROE impact on CSR of non-financial firms listed in Nigeria?
- iii. How does ROI influence CSR of non-financial firms listed in Nigeria?
- iv. How does NPM affect the CSR of non-financial firms listed in Nigeria?

The study's main goal is to look into the impact of firm performance on non-financial firms' CSR in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to investigate the impact of ROA, ROE, ROI, and NPM on the CSR of Nigerian non-financial firms. In order to achieve the goals of this study, the following null hypotheses were developed:

H₀₁: Return on asset has no significant effect on CSR of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria

H₀₂: Return on equity has no significant effect on CSR of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria

H₀₃: Return on investment has no significant effect on CSR of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria

H₀₄: Net profit margin has no significant effect on CSR of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

This study will assist management and stakeholders in the non-financial firms make informed decision regarding the extent to which to engage and or participate in providing social responsibility to the community in which they operate. The research also proffer suggestions to the human right activist on which firm attribute to pay more attention to in trying to justify the fight for firm participation in providing CSR to the community. Government will also be able to use the recommendations from the study to develop broad based policies on CSR in Nigeria. This study will also provide empirical results that would be available in literature for the benefit of government, practitioner, scholars (students of CSR) and other user of the information. Finally, recommendations from this study will add to the body of existing knowledge and enhance the quality of literature in the area of CSR in Nigeria.

2 Literature Review

There are many different definitions of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), and there is a lot of disagreement in the literature. Several authors have attempted to define this term from various perspectives. CSR, according to the World Business Council for Sustainable Development (1999), is "The business

community's ongoing commitment to act ethically and contribute to economic development while also improving the quality of life for employees and their families, as well as the local community and society as a whole." According to the World Bank, CSR is a term that describes a company's obligations to all of its stakeholders in all of its operations and activities. When making decisions, socially responsible businesses consider the full scope of their impact on communities and the environment, balancing stakeholder needs with the need to make a profit" (Nicolau, 2008).

CSR is defined as a company's responsibility to consider the environmental implications of its operations, products, and facilities, to eliminate waste and emissions, to make the most of its resources in terms of efficiency and productivity, and to minimize practices that may have an adverse impact on future generations' enjoyment of the country's resources. In the emerging global economy, where the Internet, social media, and information revolution shine light on business practices all over the world, companies are more frequently judged on their environmental responsibility. Consumers and business partners alike are curious about what goes on inside a company. Because of the transparency of business practices, CSR is no longer a luxury for many companies, but rather a necessity. 2004 (Mazurkiewicz)

Profit is, in essence, the driving force behind businesses. Firms operate in order to maximize their profits, but they also give back to the community through corporate social responsibilities. Companies strive to nurture a good and win-win relationship between CSR and their financial performance (FP) success, according to Van de Ven and Graafland (2006). Many different metrics are used to represent financial performance. They are mostly divided into two categories: ROA and ROE (Waddock & Graves, 1997; Mahoney & Roberts, 2007; & Tsoutsoura, 2004); profitability in absolute terms (Cowen, Ferrari, and Parker, 1987 in Stanwick and Sarah 1998); and multiple accounting-based measures with the overall index using a score of 0 10 (Waddock & Graves, 1997; Mahoney & Roberts, 2007; & Tsout (Moore, 2001). Mahoney and Roberts' measure is used in this study (2007). The idea behind using the measure for financial performance is that it can indicate an entity's performance that is unaffected by differences in company size.

ROA assesses not only the profit aspect of a company's financial performance, but also the assets used to generate that profit. Return on assets (ROA) is an indicator of how profitable a company is in relation to its assets. The return on assets (ROA) tells a manager, investor, or analyst how effectively a company's management is using its assets to generate profit. ROA is calculated as Net Income divided by Average Total Asset and is displayed as a percentage. $\text{Net Income} / \text{Average Total Asset} = \text{ROA}$. Singh, Murty, Gupta, and Dikshit (Singh, Murty, Gupta, & Dikshit, 2007).

Return on equity (ROE) is a measurement of a company's performance in relation to its equity, which is also known as net assets or assets minus liabilities in corporate finance.. The return on investment (ROI) is a measure of a company's ability to grow its earnings through its investments. It's a metric for financial performance that's calculated by dividing net income by shareholders' equity. ROE can be thought of as the return on net assets since shareholders' equity equals a company's assets minus its debt. The return on equity (ROE) is a measure of how well a company's assets are being used to generate profits. Any company's return on equity (ROE) can be measured if net profits and equity are both positive figures. Before dividends to common shareholders and after dividends to preferred shareholders and interest to lenders, net income is calculated. $\text{Net Income} \times \text{Average Shareholders' Equity} = \text{Return on Equity}$

The amount of income generated by a company for a given period, net of expenses and taxes, is referred to as net income. The average shareholder's equity is calculated by adding equity at the start of each period. The period's beginning and end should correspond to when the net income is earned. Return on Investment (ROI) is a performance metric that can be used to assess the efficiency of a particular investment or to compare the

efficiency of several different investments. The benefit (or return) of an investment is divided by the cost of the investment to calculate ROI. A percentage or a ratio is used to express the result. ROI is calculated using the following formula: $ROI = \text{Net Profit} / \text{Total Investment} * 100$.

Keep in mind that if you lose money on your investment, your return on investment (ROI) will be negative. This formula can be used by stockholders to calculate the return on their investment: $(\text{Net Income} + (\text{Current Value} - \text{Original Value})) / \text{Original Value} * 100 = \text{Return on Investment}$.

The net profit margin is a metric for determining a company's success in terms of revenue. A higher profit margin indicates that the company is more profitable (Adebisi, Iyiola & Olayemi, 2016). Earnings as a percentage of sales is how profit margins are expressed in ratios. Profitability of different companies can be easily compared by expressing margins as a percentage. The Net Profit Margin (NPM) is a company's ratio of net income to sales, calculated as follows: Net Profit Margin is equal to Net Income After Taxes divided by Sales.

According to Carroll's (1991) theory, CSR encompasses four major types of social responsibilities: economic, legal, ethical, and philanthropic. The economic component is concerned with the obligation to profit, and this obligation serves as the foundation for the other components. In terms of the legal aspect, society expects businesses to follow all applicable laws and regulations. Ethical responsibilities concern how society expects organizations to embrace their values and norms, even if those values and norms may be higher than those required by law. Philanthropic responsibilities are the actions that society expects from businesses in order for them to be good corporate citizens.

Legitimacy's Theory provides a more advanced perspective on CSR because it considers the businesses as they are bound by a social contract in which it states that the firms hold to perform different desired actions for the society in return for the rewards and that their objectives will be approved, which consequently guarantees the firm's continued existence (Brown & Deegan, 1998; Degan, 2002; and Guthrie & Parker, 1989).

3 Methodology

In order to address the problem of the study, this study uses correlational and ex post facto research designs. The information was taken from the sample firms' annual reports. From January 2009 to December 2018, the study's population included all 75 non-financial firms listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange, which were divided into six subsectors: consumer goods (27) firms, industrial goods (21) firms, agriculture (5) firms, conglomerate (6) firms, natural resources (5) firms, and health care (11) firms. In view of the nature of the model used in the study, a filter is employed to eliminate any firm that was listed after 2009. Consequently, 18 firms were eliminated leaving 56 firms as sample size of the study. The list of non financial firms listed in Nigeria and the sample for the study are provided in Table 1.

Table 1
Population and Sample Size

S/No	Non Financial Firms	Population	Sample Size
1.	Consumer goods	27	20
2.	Industrial goods	21	17
3.	Agriculture	5	4
4.	Conglomerate	6	4
5.	Natural Resources	5	4
6.	Health care	11	7
		75	56

Source: NSE Year Book 2018

In order to test the hypotheses formulated and to achieve the objectives of the study, the model testing the hypotheses of the study is specified as follows:

$$CSR_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ROA_{it} + \beta_2 ROE_{it} + \beta_3 ROI_{it} + \beta_4 NPM_{it} + \beta_5 FSIZE_{it} + \beta_6 FGRWT_{it} + e_{it}$$

Where:

CSR= Corporate social responsibility

ROA = Return on Asset of the sampled non-financial firms.

ROE = Return on Equity of the sampled non-financial firms

ROI = Return on investment of the sampled non-financial firms

NPM= Net profit margin of the sampled non-financial firms

FSIZE= Firm Size

FGRWT= Firm Growth

e_{it} , = error term

Measurements for the dependent, independent and control variables of the study are shown in Table 2.

Table 2

Variable	Acronym	Definition and Measurement
Independent Variables		
Return on Asset	ROA	This represents profitability and efficiency in asset usage. It will be calculated as Profit before Interest and Tax divided by Total Assets. It's a financial measure for comparing earnings to assets. (Uwuigbe <i>et al</i> , 2016).
Return on Equity	ROE	Return on Equity (ROE) is a financial performance indicator determined by dividing net profits by shareholder equity.. ROE = Net Assets/Average Shareholders' Equity. (Mailafia 2011)
Return on investment	ROI	Return on Investment (ROI) is a performance metric that can be used to calculate an investment's efficiency or to compare the efficiency of many different investments. (Hassan <i>et al</i> , 2013)
Net Profit Margin	NPM	NPM shows company's ability to generate their net sales against total net sales. It is measured as Net sales/net income (Riyanto, 1995)
Dependant Variable		
Corporate Social Responsibility	CSR	CSR is measured as natural logarithm of total cost spent on CSR by the company annually. (Abdu, 2016).
Control Variables		
Firm Size	FSIZE	Firm Size is measured as natural logarithm of total assets of the company (Babalola, 2013).
Firm Growth	FGRWT	Firms Growth is measured as change in revenue (Ahmed et al, 2011).

Variable Definition and Measurement

Source: International Accounting Journals, 2017

Table 3 shows descriptive statistics for the variables used in the study, including minimum, maximum mean, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis.

Table 3

Descriptive Statistics						
Variables	Mean	Std. Dev	Min	Max	Kurtosis	Skewness
CSR	14.041	4.543	3.439	23.565	2.371	-0.560
ROA	0.283	0.218	0.018	0.974	2.855	0.845
ROE	0.466	0.234	0.051	0.989	2.184	0.168
ROI	0.292	0.217	0.024	0.974	2.608	0.652
NPM	0.377	0.260	0.010	0.979	2.131	0.284
FSIZE	17.224	1.577	13.559	21.346	2.902	-0.172
FGT	0.311	0.970	5.501	15.573	199.970	13.220

Source: STATA OUTPUT MP VERSION 15.1, 2020

The measure of CSR of non-financial firms listed in Nigeria has a mean value of 14.041 with a standard deviation of 4.543, and minimum and maximum values of 3.439 and 23.565, respectively, as shown in Table 3. The average proportion of return on asset (ROA) was 0.283, with a standard deviation of 0.218; the minimum and maximum values were 0.018 and 0.974, respectively, according to the table.. This implies that, on average, the proportion of return on asset (ROA) as financial performance measure in non- financial sector is 22% and the data deviate from both sides of the mean by 22%. In addition, the Table also indicates an average proportion of return on equity (ROE) of 0.466 with standard deviation of 0.234, the minimum and maximum values of 0.051 and 0.989 respectively. The deviation from both sides of the mean is 23%. This also suggests a moderate dispersion of the data from the mean because the mean value is close to the standard deviation. Similarly, Table 3 above shows average return on investment (ROI) of 0.292 with standard deviation of 0.217, the minimum and maximum values are 0.024 and 0.974 respectively. This implies that an average ROI in non- financial firms listed in Nigeria is 29%. The deviation of the data from both sides of the mean is 0.217. This suggests a close dispersion of the data from the mean because the mean value is not far away from the standard deviation. The table also shows an average net profit margin (NPM) of 0.377 with a standard deviation of 0.377, with 0.010 and 0.979 as the minimum and maximum values, respectively. The table indicates an average firm size (FSZ) of 17.224 with standard deviation of 1.577, and minimum and maximum values of 13.559 and 21.346 respectively. Lastly, Table 3 above shows average firm growth (FGT) of 0.311 with standard deviation of 0.970, the minimum and maximum values are 5.501 and 15.573 respectively. This implies that an average FGT in non-financial firms listed in Nigeria is 31%. The deviation of the data from both sides of the mean is 0.970. This suggests a close dispersion of the data from the mean because the mean value is not far away from the standard deviation. The kurtosis value of 199.970 suggesting that most of the values are higher than mean, and the data does meet a normal distribution assumption; the Skewness value of 13.220 implying that the data is positively skewed (that is, most of the data are on the right side of the normal curve), implying that the data does not meet the symmetrical distribution assumption.

Therefore, the test of normal data is conducted and the results are presented in a histogram figure 1 below. Figure 1 is a histogram that tests the extent of the normal data, the figure is presented below:

Figure 1

Table 4

Correlation Matrix Result

Variables	CSR	ROA	ROE	ROI	NPM	FSIZE	FGT	VIF	T. Values
CSR	1.000								
ROA	0.409	1.000						1.080	0.928
ROE	0.015	-0.127	1.000					1.140	0.875
ROI	0.310	0.187	-0.243	1.000				1.100	0.912
NPM	0.030	-0.205	0.233	-0.132	1.000			1.100	0.911
FSIZE	0.070	-0.043	0.153	-0.005	0.064	1.000		1.030	0.969
FGT	0.088	0.015	0.073	0.007	0.026	0.082	1.000	1.010	0.988

Source: STATA OUTPUTMP VERSION 15.1, 2020

The results in Table 4 show the degree of association between the CSR and all pairs of independent variables individually and cumulatively with the dependent variable (CSR) of the study in non-financial firms listed in Nigeria. The table presents a positive and significant effect between CSR and return on asset (ROA) from the correlation coefficient of value of 0.4089. This positive and significant effect implies that, as the proportion of ROA increases the CSR of the sample firms will increase also. Based on the correlation coefficient of 0.0153 as shown in table 4, there is a positive and significant relationship between CSR of non-financial firms and ROE of the sampled firms. This positive and significant effect implies that as the proportion of ROE of the sample firms increases the CSR will also increase. Moreover, the table indicates a positive correlation between CSR and return on investment (ROI) from the correlation coefficient of 0.309. This positive and significant effect implies that, as the return on investment (ROI) increase the CSR will also improve in the same direction. The table presents a positive and significant effect between CSR and Net Profit Margin (NPM) from the correlation coefficient of value of 0.030. This positive and significant effect implies that, as the proportion of NPM increases the CSR of the sampled firms will increase also.

The analysis of the effect between dependent variable CSR and all the independent variables and between independent variables and themselves indicated that is mostly positive. However, to conclude the effect of the

dependent variable (CSR) and all the pairs of independent variables (return on asset, return on equity, return on investment and net profit margin) of Nigerian non- financial firms, the regression model of the study is analysed in the following chapter.

Table 5

Post Estimation Test Result		
Test	Chi2 values	Sig
Mean VIF	1.080	
Hottest	4912.630	0.000
Hausman	3.320	0.768
LM	0.000	1.000

Source: STATA OUTPUT MP VERSION 15.1, 2020

Multicollinearity Test: Table 5 presents the correlation matrix of the linear relationships of the independent variables and themselves. From observation, no variables with a high correlation of above 0.50, therefore, the threat is not too harsh because the correlations are both negative. To formally substantiate the absence of multicollinearity between the independent variables, colinearity diagnostics of variable inflation factor (VIF) and tolerance values (TV) are observed.

Heteroscedasticity Test: The heteroscedasticity test is used to determine whether or not the variability of error terms is constant. The presence of heteroscedasticity indicates that the error term's variation is not constant, affecting the study's best linear unbiased estimators (BLUE). The test shows that there is heteroscedasticity because the chi square probability is statistically significant at 1%, indicating that the data are not homoscedastic.

Hausman Specification Test: The result of the test reveals that they are highly correlated because the chi-square probability is not significant at any level of significant (0.9701) which guided this work to interpret the result of the random effect model see appendix I.

Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian Multiplier (LM) Random Effects Test: this test is conducted to guide the decision on which regression model best fits the study between the random effect regression model result and the OLS regression model result. This is because there is no significant difference between the two models of regression. However, the LM-significant chibar2 test of 0.0000 suggests that the randomized regression model is best suited to the study. Summary of the regression result obtained from the study model

($CSR_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1ROA_{it} + \beta_2ROE_{it} + \beta_3ROI_{it} + \beta_4NPM_{it} + \beta_5FSIZE_{it} + \beta_6FGT_{it} + e_{it}$) is presented in table 6:

Table 6

Summary of Regression Results			
Variables	Coefficients	Z-values	P-values
ROA	83.133	10.430	0.000
ROE	25.990	2.300	0.021
ROI	32.948	7.150	0.000
NPM	16.789	3.140	0.002
FSIZE	12.620	1.660	0.096
FGT	4.190	1.780	0.075
Constant	-221.666	-5.310	0.000
Wald chi2		195.840	0.000
R Square			0.262

Source: STATA OUTPUT MP VERSION 15.1, 2020

Table 6 revealed the cumulative R² (0.262) which is known as the coefficient of determination, it gives the proportion or percentage of the total variation in the dependent variable as explained by the independent variables jointly. Hence, it signifies 26% of total variation in CSR of non- financial firms listed in Nigeria is caused by the collective effort of return on asset, return on equity, return on investment and net profit margin. This further indicates that the model is fit, that the variables are correctly selected, combined and used in the study. This is statistically supported by the wald chi2 statistical coefficient of 195,840 with a p-value of 0.0000, which is statistically significant at 1%. The results from table 6 shows that, ROA has a statistically significant positive effect on the CSR of the listed non- financial firms in Nigeria, from the coefficient of 83.133 which is significant at 1% level of significance (p-value of 0.000). This suggests that, when performance as measured by ROA increases by 1%, CSR expenditure will also increases and, this implies that performance as measured by ROA is a major factor when considering CSR activities in non- financial firms in Nigerian. This result is not surprising because it is not contrary to our expectation that increase in ROA will lead to increase in the quantum of investment in CSR in the non- financial firms. The result may be for the fact that non- financial firms do hold much tangible assets in which share holders' funds is presented as assets. The result may not be contrary in the real sector of the economy where assets are utilized for production in which turnover is mostly shouldered on the productive assets. The result is also consistent with slack resource theory which states that the higher the performance the higher the investment in CSR.

The table also shows ROE has a positive impact on the CSR of the listed non- financial firms in Nigeria, from the coefficient of 25.999 which is also statistically significant at all levels of significance (p-value of 0.000). This signifies that for every increase in ROE there will be proportionate increase in CSR investment. The result is in line with my expectation that increase in ROE will lead to increase in investment in CSR in the non-financial service. The result agrees with the finding of Wijesinghe (2011), Tazul-islam (2012). However, this suggests that performance as measured by return on equity is an important factor in considering investment in CSR in non- financial firms in Nigerian since its impacts positively and significantly on the CSR of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. The board of non financial firms should come up with policies that will ensure improvement and judicious utilisation of the ROE which in the long run will continue to impact positively and also significantly on the CSR investment.

Similarly, table 6 shows that ROI has a strong positive, significant and statistical relationship with CSR as represented by the coefficient values of 32.948 which is at 1%, significant level. Therefore a company with higher ROI may likely be willing to invest more in CSR. This findings is not surprising base on the above fact and also it provides an evidence that ROI contributed significantly to investment in CSR.

The regression result in table 6 reveal that NPM has a z-value of 3.14 and a coefficient beta value of 16.799 with a significant p-value of 0.000. This signifies that NPM has a positive, significant and statistical impact on CSR of listed non- financial firms in Nigeria. This indicates that for every 1% increase in proportion of NPM, CSR will also increases. Another explanation is that the more the NPM is achieved by non- financial firms listed in Nigeria, the more they are likely going to participating in CSR. This result is not surprising as it did not contradict the researchers' expectation that NPM as a performance measure is expected to have a direct relation with participation in CSR by non- financial firms listed in Nigeria. The regression results used to test the hypotheses of the study is presented as follows:

Table 7

Hypotheses Test

Variables	Coefficients	Z-values	P-values
ROA	83.133	10.430	0.000
ROE	25.990	2.300	0.021

ROI	32.948	7.150	0.000
NPM	16.789	3.140	0.002
FSIZE	12.620	1.660	0.096
FGT	4.190	1.780	0.075

Source: STATA OUTPUT/MP VERSION 15.1, 2020

Table 7 shows all the independent variables of the study (ROA, ROE, ROI and NPM) the firm size and firm growth here are control variable. Therefore it can be observed from table 7 that the entire independent variables are statistically significant at all level of significance (1% 5% &10%) respectively. Thus; the implication here is that, the model is fit, variable properly selected, combined and used for the study. Therefore the test of individual hypothesis is presented as follows:

H₀₁: ROA has no significant impact on the CSR of listed non financial firms in Nigerian.

ROA of Nigerian listed non financial firms, the result reveal a positive and statistical relationship at 1% between ROA and CSR. Thus, the finding is line with my expectations. Therefore, in line with the result Hypothesis 1, H₀₁, is rejected. H₀₂ ROE has no significant influence on the CSR of listed non financial firms in Nigerian. With respect to the ROE measured by the proportion of profit after tax to the total equity holding of Nigerian listed non financial firms, the result reveals that ROE is positively and statistically related to CSR of Nigerian listed non financial firms at 1% level of significance. The finding is not surprising both on sign and effect. Thus, this provides an evidence of rejecting Hypothesis 2 of the study. Thus Hypothesis 2 is rejected. H₀₃ ROI has no significant effect on the CSR of listed non financial firms in Nigeria. The result of ROI is not contrary at all. ROI as a measured by profit after tax to total investment, reveals a positive and statistical association at 1% with CSR of Nigerian listed non financial firms. Therefore this finding provides evidence of rejecting Hypothesis 3 of the study. As such Hypothesis 3 is rejected. H₀₄ NPM has no significant impact on the CSR of listed non financial firms in Nigerian. Finally NPM was found to have a positive, significant and statistical influence on CSR of Nigerian listed non financial firms at all level of significance. However, this finding was found to be consistent with our priory expectations. Therefore, this result forms the basis of rejecting Hypothesis 4. Thus Hypothesis 4 is rejected.

5 Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the discussion and analysis in the preceding paragraphs, the study concludes as follows: First, the study has provided both empirical and statistical evidence on the use of four explanatory variables of ROA, ROE, ROI and NPM in predicting the explained variable (CSR) of the sampled firms. Secondly, ROA plays a major role in improving the CSR of non-financial firms listed in Nigeria positively. Thirdly, it was found that a positive association exists between ROE and CSR of non financial firms listed in Nigeria. This suggests that ROE plays a famous role in improving the CSR of non- financial firms listed in Nigeria. Therefore, the higher the proportion of ROE in non- financial firms listed in Nigeria is likely to enhance their participation in CSR of the firms. Fourthly, it was found that a positive relationship exists between ROI and CSR of non financial firms listed in Nigeria. This suggests that, ROI take part in improving the CSR of non- financial firms listed in Nigeria. Therefore, higher ROI of non- financial firms listed in Nigeria is likely to enhance their contribution in CSR. Finally, NPM was found to have a positive impact on the CSR of the sample firms. Also, firms with substantial amount of NPM were found to be stronger in improving the sampled firms' participation in CSR. The following recommendations are made in light of the study's findings and conclusions.: The management of non-financial firms should ensure that: The ROA as well as ROE are maintained because they were found to improve the firms' participation in CSR, there is also the need for the management of non- financial firms listed in Nigeria to increase their level of ROI, this will promote their participation in CSR, and the management of non-financial firms are also advice to improve their NPM; this will promote their participation in CSR.

References

- i Abdu, A. (2014). *Financial performance and CSR of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria*, An unpublished seminar, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria-Nigeria.
- ii Ahmad, Z., Hassan, S., & Mohammad, J. (2003). *Determinants of environmental reporting in Malaysia*. *International Journal of Business Studies*, 11(1), 69–80.
- iii Akindele, R.I (2011). *CSR: An organizational tool for survival in Nigeria*. <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/ifep/article/view/69516>
- iv Akrouf, M. Akrouf & Ben-Othman, M. (2013). *Determinants of corporate environmental disclosure in MENA emerging markets*, *Journal of Reviews on Global Economies*, 2: 46-59.
- v Al-shubiri, F. N., Al-abadallat, A. Z., & Orabi, M. M. A. (2012). *Financial and non-financial determinants of CSR*. *Asian Economic and Financial Review* 2(8), 1001 – 1012.
- vi Bailey, D., Harte, G., & Sugden, R. (2000). *Corporate disclosure and the deregulation of international investment*. *Accounting, Auditing and Accountability Journal*, 13(2), 197 – 218.
- vii Barako, D. G. (2006). *Factors influencing voluntary corporate disclosure by Kenyan companies, corporate governance: An International Review*, 14 (2), 107-125.
- viii Chen, K. H., & Metcalfe R. W. (1980). *The relationship between pollution control records and financial indicators revisited*, *The Accounting Review*, 55(1), 168–177.
- ix David, A.O. (2012). *An assessment of the impact of CSR on the Nigerian society: the examples of Nigerian banking and communication industries*, *Universal Journal of Marketing and Business Research* 1(1), 017-043.
- x Deegan, C. (2002). *The legitimizing effect of social and environmental disclosures – a theoretical foundation*. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 15(3), 282–311.
- xi El Ghoul, S., O. Guedhami, C. Kwok & D. Mishra, (2011). *Does CSR affect the cost of capital?* *Journal of Banking and Finance* 35, 2388-2408.
- xii Elsayed, K. & Paton, D.,(2005). *The impact of environmental performance on firm performance: static and dynamic panel data evidence*. *Structural Change and Economic Dynamics* 16 (3), 395-412.
- xiii Fauzi, H., Mahoney, L & Abdul Rahman, A. (2007). *Institutional ownership and corporate social performance: empirical evidence from Indonesian companies*, *Issues in Social and Environmental Accounting* 1 (2) 334-347.
- xiv Guthrie, J., & Parker, L. (1989). *Corporate social reporting: a rebuttal of legitimacy theory*. *Accounting and Business Review*, 19(3), 343–352.
- xv Hackston, D. & Milne, M. J. (1996). *Some determinant of social and environment disclosures in New Zealand company*, *Accounting, Audit, and Accountability Journal*.
- xvi Ismail, Z. & Koh B.E. (1999). *On CSR disclosure (CSR D) in Singapore*, A paper presented in Third International Conference on International Accounting and Management Issues, Bangalore, India
- xvii Jamali, D., Zanhour, M., & Keshishian, T. (2009). *Peculiar strengths and relational attributes of SMEs in the context of CSR*. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 87, 355-377.
- xviii Kaplan, R. S. & Norton D. P.(2001). *Transforming the balanced scorecard from performance measurement to strategic management: Part 1*, *Accounting Horizon* 15(1), 87–104.limited.
- xix Li, W. & Zhang, R. (2010). *CSR, ownership structure and political interference: evidence from Chinese*, *Journal of Business Ethics*, (96) 631-645.
- xx Mahoney, L.S. & Roberts, R.W. (2007). *Corporate social performance, financial performance and institutional ownership in Canadian firms*. *Accounting Forum*, 31(3): 233-253.
- xxi McGuire, J. B, Sundgren, A. & Schneeweis, T. *CSR and firm financial performance*. *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 31, No. 4, 854-872.

- xxii Naser, K., Al-Khatib, K. & Karbhari, R. (2002). *Empirical evidence on the depth of corporate information disclosure in developing countries: the case of Jordan*. *International Journal of Commerce and Management*, 12 (3 & 4), 122-155.
- xxiii Oguntade, A., & Mafimisebi, S. (2011). *Contributions of CSR to agriculture and rural development in Nigeria*. *Journal of sustainable Development in Africa*, 13 (3), pp 110-128.
- xxiv Olowokudejo F. & Aduloju S.A. (2011). *CSR and organizational effectiveness of insurance companies in Nigeria*. Retrieved from [http:// www.emeraldinsight.com/1526-5943.htm](http://www.emeraldinsight.com/1526-5943.htm) July 2017 *International Studies*, Issue 12, 4-20.
- xxv Paek, S., Xiao, Q., Lee, S., & Song, H. (2013) *Does managerial ownership affect different CSR dimensions? an empirical examination of U.S. publicly traded hospitality firms*. *Forthcoming International Journal of Hospitality Management*, pp.1-11.
- xxvi Rahman, A.& Widyasari, K. N. (2008). *The analysis of company characteristic influence toward CSR disclosure: empirical evidence of manufacturing companies listed in JSX*”, *JurnalAkuntansi& Auditing Indonesia*, 12 (1)
- xxvii Sarlija, N. & Harc, M. (2012). *The impact of liquidity on the capital structure: A case study of Croatian firms*. *Business Systems Research*, Vol. 3, No. 1, pp. 30-36.
- xxviii Tsoutsoura, M. (2004). *CSR and financial performance*. University of California, Berkeley: Working Paper Series. <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/111799p2>
- xxix Ullmann, A. (1985). *Data in search of a theory: a critical examination of the relationship among social performance, social disclosure, and economic performance of US firms*, *Academy of Management Review* 10 (3), 540-577).
- xxx Vincent O. M. (2012). *The impact of corporate environmental responsibility on financial performance; perspective from the multinational extractive sector*.
- xxxi World Business Council for Sustainable Development, (1999). *CSR: meeting changing expectations*. World Business Council for Sustainable Development, Geneva.
- xxxii Wulayo, W. (2017). *Firm size, firm age and firm growth on CSR in Indonesia: the case of real estate companies*. *European Research Studies Journal*, Vol. XX; Issue 4A 2017. 360-369.
- xxxiii Yao, S., Wang, J. & Song, L. (2011). *Determinants of CSR definitions, CSR and environmental responsibility disclosure of listed Chinese firms*, *Discussion paper* 72.
- xxxiv Yusoff, I., & Adamu, B.S. (2016). *The relationship between CSR; Evidence from Malaysia*. *International Business Management* 10(4), 345-351.
- xxxv Zu, L. & Song, L. (2009). *Determinants of managerial value on CSR: Evidence from China*, *Journal of Business Ethics* (88), 105 – 113.

APPENDIX

DESCRIPTIVE

. sum csr roa roe roi npm fsize fgt

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
csr	560	14.04096	4.542666	3.4387	23.56508
roa	560	.2833069	.2175071	.0001835	.97426
roe	560	.4655174	.2342977	.005117	.9887874
roi	560	.2917681	.2174453	.0002401	.9742501
npm	560	.3767823	.2599751	.0000101	.9791925
fsize	560	17.2235	1.57681	13.55933	21.34578
fgt	560	.3111674	.9702808	5.50e-06	15.5731

. sum csr roa roe roi npm fsize fgt,detail

CSR

Percentiles	Smallest		
1%	3.565966	3.4387	
5%	6.003403	3.441538	
10%	6.457793	3.449478	Obs 560
25%	9.407857	3.482588	Sum of wgt. 560
50%	14.93092		Mean 14.04096
		Largest	Std. Dev. 4.542666
75%	17.41008	23.43521	
90%	18.66488	23.48201	Variance 20.63581
95%	19.88684	23.48201	Skewness -.5596427
99%	22.51604	23.56508	Kurtosis 2.371271

ROA

Percentiles	Smallest		
1%	.0053088	.0001835	
5%	.031679	.0003989	
10%	.0608479	.0003989	Obs 560
25%	.109536	.0005251	Sum of wgt. 560
50%	.2061227		Mean .2833069
		Largest	Std. Dev. .2175071
75%	.454992	.9295439	
90%	.6062756	.9295439	Variance .0473093
95%	.6950738	.9622	Skewness .8452255
99%	.88762	.97426	Kurtosis 2.855122

ROE

Percentiles	Smallest		
1%	.0376808	.005117	
5%	.1088769	.0083372	
10%	.1373225	.0311297	Obs 560
25%	.2823068	.0313	Sum of wgt. 560
50%	.456447		Mean .4655174
		Largest	Std. Dev. .2342977
75%	.644374	.9847645	
90%	.7967867	.9860136	Variance .0548954
95%	.8746849	.9868327	Skewness .1675398
99%	.977219	.9887874	Kurtosis 2.183847

ROI

Percentiles		Smallest		
1%	.0019806	.0002401		
5%	.0148403	.0002633		
10%	.0297127	.0003487	Obs	560
25%	.121601	.0007175	Sum of wgt.	560
50%		.2333084	Mean	.2917681
75%		.463954	Std. Dev.	.2174453
90%		.57878	Variance	.0472825
95%		.6879019	Skewness	.6523598
99%		.8242914	Kurtosis	2.607729

NPM

Percentiles		Smallest		
1%	.0002602	.0000101		
5%	.0148255	.000032		
10%	.0415346	.0000835	Obs	560
25%	.124872	.0001117	Sum of wgt.	560
50%		.3665615	Mean	.3767823
75%		.564774	Std. Dev.	.2599751
90%		.7374285	Variance	.067587
95%		.83774	Skewness	.2839395
99%		.9760368	Kurtosis	2.130677

FSIZE

Percentiles		Smallest		
1%	13.55933	13.55933		
5%	14.37957	13.55933		
10%	14.87397	13.55933	Obs	560
25%	16.2054	13.55933	Sum of wgt.	560
50%		17.36646	Mean	17.2235
75%		18.2257	Std. Dev.	1.57681
90%		18.89602	Variance	2.486329
95%		19.54236	Skewness	-.1715922
99%		21.34578	Kurtosis	2.902937

FGT

Percentiles		Smallest		
1%	.001316	5.50e-06		
5%	.009837	.000114		
10%	.0182325	.000557	Obs	560
25%	.0421855	.001164	Sum of wgt.	560
50%		.1295	Mean	.3111674
75%		.3431465	Std. Dev.	.9702808
90%		.6692065	Variance	.9414448
95%		.73585	Skewness	13.21992
99%		2.45131	Kurtosis	199.9702

REGRESSION

. correlate csr roa roe roi npm fisze fgt
(obs=560)

	csr	roa	roe	roi	npm	fisze	fgt
csr	1.0000						
roa	0.4089	1.0000					
roe	0.0153	-0.1274	1.0000				
roi	0.3098	0.1871	-0.2434	1.0000			
npm	0.0297	-0.2050	0.2331	-0.1323	1.0000		
fisze	0.0700	-0.0433	0.1526	-0.0051	0.0638	1.0000	
fgt	0.0883	0.0153	0.0734	0.0074	0.0258	0.0819	1.0000

. reg csr roa roe roi npm fisze fgt

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs =	560
Model	6079320.76	6	1013220.13	F(6, 553) =	32.64
Residual	17166488.6	553	31042.4748	Prob > F =	0.0000
				R-squared =	0.2615
				Adj R-squared =	0.2535
Total	23245809.3	559	41584.6321	Root MSE =	176.19

csr	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
roa	83.13316	7.970545	10.43	0.000	67.47692 98.78941
roe	25.98962	11.2873	2.30	0.022	3.818385 48.16086
roi	32.94845	4.611294	7.15	0.000	23.89066 42.00625
npm	16.78935	5.339358	3.14	0.002	6.301448 27.27726
fisze	12.61953	7.582202	1.66	0.097	-2.273906 27.51297
fgt	4.189655	2.353264	1.78	0.076	-.4327742 8.812085
_cons	-221.6649	41.7079	-5.31	0.000	-303.5902 -139.7396

. vif

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
roe	1.14	0.875070
npm	1.10	0.911079
roi	1.10	0.911677
roa	1.08	0.928482
fisze	1.03	0.969072
fgt	1.01	0.988247
Mean VIF	1.08	

. hettest

Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity
 Ho: Constant variance
 Variables: fitted values of csr

chi2(1) = 4912.63
 Prob > chi2 = 0.0000

. xtreg csr roa roe roi npm fisze fgt,fe

Fixed-effects (within) regression
 Group variable: year
 Number of obs = 560
 Number of groups = 10
 R-sq: within = 0.2628
 between = 0.2031
 overall = 0.2615
 Obs per group: min = 56
 avg = 56.0
 max = 56
 F(6,544) = 32.31
 Prob > F = 0.0000
 corr(u_i, xb) = -0.0343

csr	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
roa	83.19236	8.027889	10.36	0.000	67.4229	98.96182
roe	25.50557	11.31796	2.25	0.025	3.273312	47.73783
roi	33.47922	4.656039	7.19	0.000	24.3332	42.62524
npm	16.39358	5.368746	3.05	0.002	5.847572	26.9396
fisze	12.88808	7.610637	1.69	0.091	-2.061752	27.83792
fgt	4.365961	2.364637	1.85	0.065	-.2789775	9.010899
_cons	-224.5163	41.85178	-5.36	0.000	-306.7272	-142.3054
sigma_u	21.326043					
sigma_e	176.45607					
rho	.01439626	(fraction of variance due to u_i)				

F test that all u_i=0: F(9, 544) = 0.81 Prob > F = 0.6035

. xtreg csr roa roe roi npm fisze fgt,re

Random-effects GLS regression
 Group variable: year
 Number of obs = 560
 Number of groups = 10
 R-sq: within = 0.2627
 between = 0.2072
 overall = 0.2615
 Obs per group: min = 56
 avg = 56.0
 max = 56
 wald chi2(6) = 195.84
 Prob > chi2 = 0.0000
 corr(u_i, x) = 0 (assumed)

csr	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]	
roa	83.13316	7.970545	10.43	0.000	67.51118	98.75515
roe	25.98962	11.2873	2.30	0.021	3.86691	48.11233
roi	32.94845	4.611294	7.15	0.000	23.91048	41.98642
npm	16.78935	5.339358	3.14	0.002	6.324402	27.2543
fisze	12.61953	7.582202	1.66	0.096	-2.24131	27.48038
fgt	4.189655	2.353264	1.78	0.075	-.4226574	8.801968
_cons	-221.6649	41.7079	-5.31	0.000	-303.4109	-139.9189
sigma_u	0					
sigma_e	176.45607					
rho	0	(fraction of variance due to u_i)				

